

CS 4530/CS 5500 Homeworks

HOMEWORK 4

Due: Friday, 20 November 2020, Noon Eastern Time

Revision History:

- Initial Version: 6 November 2020
- 11/8: Updated `SorterFactory` in the handout to return `BubbleSorter` as a default sorter for easier testing. -JB
- 11/10: Clarified that the spec does not require that the sorter be stable (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Stable_sorts"). -JB

Homework 4 consists of several tasks related to testing. In this assignment, you will practice test-driven-development to create two sorting implementations.

This is an individual assignment, but you may seek help about installing and using the TypeScript toolset, or about the TypeScript language itself. See the section on getting help ([../description.html#getting-help](#)) on the course description web page. Your solution may not depend on any third party libraries other than those provided in the handout archive (you may not `npm install` any packages to use for this assignment). You must implement each task entirely in the files (do not create additional source files).

To get started, please download the starter code ([hw4.zip](#))

Task 1: Writing Functional Tests (70 Points)

Consider the interface below, which specifies an `ISorter` that sorts the elements of an array of elements in place. The sorter can sort any type `E`, provide that a suitable function is provided for comparing elements of type `E`.

```
export default interface ISorter {  
  /**  
   * @param list a list to be sorted (in place: the sort functi  
   * @param compareFunction is a function that takes two argume  
   */  
  sort(list: E[], compareFunction: (x: E, y: E) => number) : vo  
}
```

Please note that while the sorter must update the order of the elements in the input list (and not return a new list), the sorting algorithm need not be a stable sorting algorithm

(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Category:Stable_sorts") (Added 11/10).

Your first task is to apply functional/black-box testing techniques to create a suite of at least 10 tests to test this interface thoroughly. Write these tests and place them in your solution in the file `test/task1/BlackboxTests.ts`. In your tests, you should assume that you can obtain an `ISorter` object by using the method `sorterFactory.createSorter()` that we have provided. When we test your tests, we'll change the `Sorter` that is returned by the factory. You can run these tests locally on our default sorter by running `npm test`.

Recall that the goal of black-box testing is to create tests for a system only considering *the specification of that system*. To help you assess whether your tests cover all of the expected behaviors that a sorter might exhibit, we have created a suite of sorters with *known* bugs. You can not see the sorters (and we will not tell you what their bugs are), but when you submit your tests to GradeScope, we will automatically run your tests on each of our buggy implementations. Our goal is for you to think hard about what tests to write, then write them, then submit them to GradeScope. Hence, we are imposing a submission cap for this assignment: you may only submit your code to GradeScope a maximum of five times in a rolling 24 hour period. Note that if you start early, you could submit 5 times a day, every day, until the deadline.

Grading breakdown for this task:

- Defect coverage: We have prepared 12 buggy sorters. At least one

of your tests should fail on our buggy sorters, but pass on our correct sorters. To receive any points for this component, your test suite *must* pass on our correct sorter implementations (48 points; autograded)

- Overall test quality, judged manually (22 points)

Task 2: Implementing Sorters, Structural Coverage (30 Points)

Your next task is to create two subclasses of the `Sorter` interface that implement sorting algorithms of your choice. These algorithms must be efficient (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sorting_algorithm#Efficient_sorts) in the sense that they perform, on average, $O(n \log n)$ comparisons to sort n items. For example, one of these could implement a `QuickSorter` class that uses C.A.R. Hoare's famous *QuickSort* algorithm.

Provide your two implementations in `src/task2/Sorter1.ts` and `src/task2/Sorter2.ts`. Create tests for each implementation in the files `test/task2/Sorter1Tests.spec.ts` and `test/task2/Sorter2Tests.spec.ts` respectively. You may choose to build these tests suites by copying tests from your `BlackboxTests.ts`, although since you now have the source code for the sorters, you can also write tests that cover the specific behavior of each sorter. Run these test suites to ensure that your sorters behave as expected.

Enhance your test suite as necessary to ensure that your tests achieve 100% statement coverage when run on your sorters. Note that we have pre-configured the project to collect and display coverage when you run `npm test`.

Grading breakdown for this task:

- Sorter correctness: your two sorters should pass our comprehensive test suite (10 points, autograded)
- Structural coverage: your tests should have 100% statement coverage on your sorters (10 points, autograded)
- Overall code quality, judged manually (10 points)

Questions

Please post all questions on Piazza (<https://piazza.com/northeastern/fall2020/cs4530and5500>).

Grading

Your assignment will be checked automatically, to ensure that it builds correctly and that the tests pass. In addition, it will be checked manually, to ensure that it correctly implements the tasks above, and it will also be inspected for general coding conventions, code quality issues, and test suite quality. Please see the details under each task for a more precise grade breakdown.

Submitting Your Solution

Submit your solution using Gradescope (<https://www.gradescope.com/courses/147682>). Create a zip file of your entire solution (containing both your `src` and `test` directories) that does *not* contain your `node_modules` directory (which is likely quite large). The easiest way to accomplish this is to run the included `npm script` in your solution directory: `run npm run-script pack`, which should produce the file `cs4530-5500-fall-2020-hw4.zip`. Other archive formats are not accepted by GradeScope; please note that `npm pack` may be a solution that you find through Google, but that it will generate a `.tar.gz` file, which will not be accepted by GradeScope: please run `npm run-script pack`. After you submit your assignment, Gradescope will automatically compile your code and run our suite of automated tests. You should verify that the result that Gradescope generates is what you expect. Your code is built and tested in an Ubuntu 18 VM, using NodeJS v14. **You may submit your code to Gradescope only 5 times within a 24 hour period.** If you exceed this rate limit, any new submissions will receive the autograde results from your previous submission, and you will see a message in GradeScope along the lines of "ERROR: Your new submission was not graded. You have been rate limited. You may only submit 5 times within a 24 hour window. You will be able to submit again after 11/5/2020, 8:09:56 PM". Please contact the course staff via Piazza if you have any broken submissions (that do not get assigned a grade by the autograder), and we will ensure that these submissions do not count to your submission limit.

Please be reminded of the course late submission policy: assignments will be accepted up to 48 hours past the deadline at a penalty of 50%, and not accepted beyond 48 hours past the deadline.

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